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D3.4 Panel Management

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the content and the features of the panel management tool, as they are implemented in the VITALISE project. Panel management is referred to the coordination and research of a group of people, in our case the whole spectrum of Living Lab stakeholders, that receive services from an organization, in our case the Living Lab. VITALISE designs and implements an ICT tool that is used by Living Labs to facilitate the Panel management work such as organize research activities, schedule events, organize communications with stakeholders and keep track of these events. The purpose of this document is to present in detail all the implemented features in the panel management ICT tool, named thePanelLab (<https://app.thepanelab.com/>).

The paneLab supports an easy and well-structured digital workspace. It has an easy login procedure and clear content and menu, including the main features of the tool that are the contacts, projects and events. Through contacts, it provides an easy access to the stakeholders' names, contact information and previous interactions as well as gives the opportunity to add new members or change existing information. In "projects" the user can have access to the already existing projects of a Living Lab as well as add a new project the Living Lab organization. The feature "events", allows the user to organize and keep track of activities and user engagement for upcoming and past Living Lab events. The tool also provides a feedback form for collecting information about new features requested by the users or changes in the existing features. Researchers of the VITALISE already use the panel management in their Living Labs and provide useful feedback and practical advice for the better implementation of the panel in research activities.

The paneLab is a fully functional web application, that consists of the Back-End, which is responsible for the handling of data, and the Front-End which is a User Interface for the Back-End. The VITALISE team is constantly working towards implementing and integrating additional functionalities as requested by the Living Lab community.

Within the context of VITALISE, the paneLab is used to support the management and planning of the VITALISE Living Lab panels and facilitate the communications for the upcoming real-life testing of the Joint Research Activities. The tool will be used also by external researchers that will join VITALISE Living Labs for Transnational Access visits.

1 Introduction

1.1 A summary of panel management

“Panel management” as a term is used in healthcare as well as in business. Panel management is referred to the coordination and research of a group of people that receive services from an organization. The term “organization” is used to describe an entity that uses the panel management tool. In the current deliverable is referred to a separate Living Lab each time, but it can be extended to other research labs, research infrastructures or companies that want to handle their own panel. The group of people can be either end users or a group of consumers for a company, or policy makers, business developers, researchers with clinical expertise and a variety of other customer. The end users are people who voluntarily participate in research activities after giving informed consent to be the subject of the research. As presented in D2.1 Standard Version 1 and in D2.8 First version of user requirements, the panel management tool is consisted of an existing group of pre-screened people (e.g., patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Living Labs can use the panel management tool as a digital infrastructure to organize research activities, schedule events, reach contacts and find valuable data for previous research activities and members interactions -information that can be written in panel management by researchers- and have a structured data base for future-planned research activities. The use of an ICT tool for panel management can offer an important decrease in time and efforts required by panel managers and researchers, as the processes for planning future research activities and previous gathered data can be tracked in a systematic way, in short time and effectively. In this document we present the content and the features of the panel management tool, as they are implemented in the VITALISE project. Our aim is to create an innovative, reliable and state-of-the-art tool in the field of panel management ICT tools, that will combine all the needs of the researchers of Living Labs. However, our aim is not only to reassure a valuable panel lab tool via PC or laptop but to create a holistic ICT tool for all digital devices. The panel management application for iOs and smartphones is one of next steps, in accordance with the needs of researchers and the demanding research activities of the LLs.

As presented in D2.8 First version of user requirements, the VITALISE panel management tool has two types of users, the “Admin User” that is a “super user” and has access to all the information in the system, and the “Customer. Each organization-Living Lab will handle its own panel information that consists of “Customer” users.

A “customer” user type can be one of the following:

- **Owner:** is the owner of an organization. The person responsible for the specific organization and all the procedures that the organization performs in the panel management tool.
- **Manager:** the manager is assigned by the owner and is a user that can invite people to an organization or assign new managers.
- **Member:** a user that is an approved member of an organization. The member is a stakeholder of the organization that participates in projects, events and studies.

In the deliverable D2.8 First version of user requirements, there was a reference to additional user types, namely invited, applicant, seceder and exile. These user types are not referred in the current deliverable as they are not in use.

For demonstration purposes, the reader can access the panel management tool in the web address: <https://app.thepanelab.com/>, and connect by using one of the following user names: owner1, manager1, member1, member2, member3. The password is the same as the username and each account has the user type indicated by the username (e.g. owner1 is Owner type). The organization is Vitalise H2020 Demo, for respecting privacy issues. A video demonstration can be found here <https://youtu.be/kBC1e4pS0as>.

2 Panel Management features

The panel management tool is an innovative digital tool that combines simplicity and efficacy in organizing contacts, scheduling research events and activities, as well as checking the availability of the participants who has been invited. In the webpage that is already available (<https://app.thepanelab.com/>) the user can entry the tool by providing either a username or an email address.

Figure 1. The panel management.

2.1 Login procedure

For every organization, the Admin creates an Owner account. After this procedure, the owner of the organization can add the managers profiles by providing to the system their emails and a particular code for every manager account. After that, the managers of the organization can activate and login to their personal accounts in the panel management tool. The user can click on the choice “forgot password”, then provide his email address and a link will be sent automatically to user’s email address. The link will be provided by participate4campaigns@gmail.com and will be “available” (the user can open the link) within the next 24 hours. By clicking the link, the user can insert his final and individual password.

2.2 Description and general features of panel management

We will present a fully detailed description of each feature of the panel management, from manager’s perspective. After the login procedure, the user can click to “sign in” and he will be transported to the initial page of the panel management (Figure 2).

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Figure 2. The main page of panel management.

In the left side of the panel lab, the user can see the three main contents of the tool: the contacts, the projects, and the events. The user can edit his own profile by selecting the small image which is above and right on the user's name and the figure of the user (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The main page of the panel management: the profile feature

There is a symbol (*) in the information that is required to allow the user to press the choice "save" for his profile information (Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4. The profile settings in the panel management: required information are marked with (*)

Figure 5. The profile settings in the panel management: required information are marked with (*)

The three lines () icon in the main page of the panel management tool enable to maximize the main (white coloured) page of the panel and hide the dark-coloured part of the menu. This feature creates the sense of a bigger digital environment with clear contents. This feature remains in every page of the panel management.

The symbol with four arrows () offers a full maximization of the panel management screen in the user's device. This feature enables the maximization of the panel management page in user's screen in a way that the user can see only the panel in his/her screen.

The symbol of "search" () gives the opportunity to search for a specific page or contact. The user can close anytime the search bar by pressing "x" (exit).

The last symbol on the right of the main page of the panel management () provides a feedback form (Figure 6). As the panel management tool is still a prototype being tested by VITALISE Living Labs, this feature is very important for future improvements. With this feature, the user can write his/her experience with the panel management tool, their issues or problems, their likes or dislikes and possible ideas for improvement. This form has three fields:

- Title: a brief title of the issue.
- Explain the issue/ Submit a Proposal: the user can explain his/her issue with the platform, or any disturbance caused as well as, he can submit his own needs and ideas for solution to the problem.
- Select feedback type: it has two (2) choices, the “Suggestion” and the “Problem”. The user can select and guide the developer of the panel management tool whether his feedback is a suggestion for improvement or a problem that caused some inconvenience. By this way, the developers receive and directly categorize the type of feedbacks that is received, in order for them to make the appropriate changes, improvements and adjustments.

Figure 6. The feedback form in the panel management

2.3 Main content of the Panel Management

2.3.1 Contacts

On the left dark-coloured bar, it appears the first feature with the name “contacts” (Figure 7)¹. By clicking on it, the user will be automatically transferred to a new page with all the contacts available under the specific organization. All the contacts are written in alphabetical order. The user can see the name and the status of each contact.

Each contact can have one of the following status as mentioned in the section 1.1 A summary of panel management above: manager, member and owner.

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¹ Note: The names on the figure 7 as well as in other figures on this document, are given for the aims of the deliverable by researchers of the VITALISE AUTH team and research associates of the Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation AUTH.

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Figure 7. The page of contacts in the panel management

On the right side of the page, the feature “+ Add” offers the opportunity to add your new contacts (Figure 7). By clicking it, the user can write all the information of a new contact as well as the name of the project in which the contact will be or had participated. A manager (e.g. a research associate of an organization) can add new “members” in the platform. However, a manager cannot add a new “manager” or “owner”; the owner can add new managers. The symbol (*) is again referred to the information that is required to be provided by the manager to save the new member.

Each contact has a variety of helpful information, that can be stored and facilitate current and future research activities of Living Labs (Figure 9).

Figure 8. The main page of a contact in the panel management

Except from the name and the age of the participant, there are the following features:

- **Summary:** it is associated with the description that has been provided.

- **Projects:** refers to the projects that this contact has participated or is linked to.
- **Details:** In “details” the manager has the ability to provide some additional information by selecting the feature “Edit” which is on the right side of the screen (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Details in contacts

Interactions: A detailed description of members' interaction activities with projects. The aim of this feature is to create and offer a detailed “history” of the interactions that the among the users and the management team. In that way, the manager can personalize the contact and the member feels better engaged in the team. In the Interaction feature, the manager can select the choice “+ Add” and a new window will appear with the details of member's participation or interaction to a project or to a research activity (Figure 10). This new window offers the ability to the manager to write the “Title”, the “Date” and the “Interaction type” (In person/ phone/ Email/ SMS/Message /Other) of each contact. On the right side, there is the “Interaction rate” that offers the ability to rate the quality² of the interaction. In the feature “Interaction projects” the manager can add the project in which the member has participated. There is also the opportunity to write detailed descriptions and information in a box (Figure 10 “Insert text here”). The user can write and store a variety of information he/she would like to have for each member (for instance, previous member's participation or experience to other project activities).

² The term “quality” reflects the objective point of view of the manager (e.g. researcher's perspective and perception of the interaction with a member).

Figure 10. The feature of interactions in the panel management

2.3.2 Projects

Through this content feature of the panel management tool, the user can have access to the already existing projects as well as has the ability to add a new project that wants to “run” in his/her Living Lab. This feature offers all the vital and useful information that a researcher needs to know. A user-manager can search for a project in the search bar that appears in the middle of the screen. Above the user can see all the existing projects that have been added by other researchers-managers of the panel management tool (Figure 11).

Figure 11. The page of projects in the panel management

At the right side of the search bar there are also two features:

- **+Add:** the manager can add a new project. By selecting this feature, the user can add all the information about a project: the title and a description of the project, the start and the end date. The features that have the symbol (*) are required for the manager to press the button “save” and save his/her action. There is a choice between a variety of colours that can be used e.g., correspondingly to the main colour of the project’s logo.

- **Show inactive:** gives the opportunity to “hide” a project (for instance, a project that has been expired or a project that will start in a future period). When the user slides the feature “show inactive” on the right, all the projects will appear; (Figure 11). The projects that are activated have a green checkmark on the right side of each project’s box. The projects that are inactivated will still appear on the screen but without being coloured and in that case, the checkmark is grey (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Projects in the panel management. "Show inactive" mode

In addition, each project has its own bar with a feature called “Details”. By clicking on this feature, a new page appears with all the information about the project. The offered bar “search” gives the opportunity to find a particular manager or member of this project. In the right side of the search bar, the user can also see the following features:

- **All:** all the managers and members linked to a project.
- **Managers:** the managers in a project.
- **Members:** the members of a project, for instance, people who have been invited or participated to a project.

In “**Projects**”, there is also a feature called “Actions” allowing the manager to send an email to a particular manager or member, or all the people who are linked to the project. By this feature, a manager can inform, invite, give useful feedback, and communicate directly with other project’s participants or managers and research associates, without spending valuable time to search each project’s contacts via his/her email.

2.3.3 Events

The feature “**Events**”, enables the user and researcher to plan and schedule any research activity of the LLs effectively and in a short period of time. Organizing research activities is a demanding procedure of any research, hence, the best and reliable way to schedule an event is of high

importance for the validity and reliability of the research. All the events appear on the screen (Figure 13).

Start date ↑	End date	Title	Description	Location
10 Mar 2020, 20:03		Χαμός		ΑΠΘ
15 Mar 2020, 20:03	15 Mar 2020, 20:03	Δοκιμή Ευδοκίμος		Kafe Z, Thessaloniki, Greece
15 Mar 2020, 20:03	19 Mar 2020, 20:03	Επικοινωνία με Κοινότητα		
31 Mar 2020, 20:03	31 Mar 2020, 20:03	Ενεργόι πολίτες SISCODE		Ιολογικό
15 Apr 2020, 20:04	15 Apr 2020, 20:04	Coffe CoVid-19		
01 Jun 2020, 00:06	01 Jun 2020, 00:06	1st session (online)		online
15 Jun 2020, 00:06	15 Jun 2020, 00:06	June session: Environment		skype
17 Jun 2020, 00:06	17 Jun 2020, 00:06	June session: citizens		
18 Jun 2020, 00:06	18 Jun 2020, 00:06	June session: Health		skype
01 Jul 2020, 00:07	15 Jul 2020, 00:07	weekly communication		

Figure 13. The main page of Events in panel management

There are several features that allows the user to select the appropriate way -according to existing needs each time- to see all the events. The user can press “Start date”, “End date” as well as “Title”, and the events will appear in several ways in correspondence to each choice. There is a feature called “Description” to offer some brief information about each event as well as, the “Location” that informs the user in what form or place, took or will take place each event (for instance, it can be in a particular place/location or virtually such as via Skype, Webex, etc.).

On the right side of the screen in the “Events”, the user can select the following features:

- **Show inactive:** offers to a manager the choice to “hide” an event which is currently “inactive” (for instance, an event that is in the process to be planned, etc.). When the user slides the feature “show inactive” on the right, all the events will be appeared on the screen. The “inactive” events, however, will appear written in a discreet grey colour whereas the “active” events appear in black colour.
- **+Add:** this choice is for adding all the useful and vital information of an event; title, start and end date, description, location, URL and a brief description of an event (0-1000 characters) (Figure 14).

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Figure 14. The page that appears to "+Add". The required information to add an event

When opening an event (by pressing the arrow symbol on the right side of each event's bar), the user can see the information of each event (title, start and end date, etc.), (as presented in Figure 15). On the right side of the table of each event that has been selected, there is a search bar for "Participants". The manager can search a particular member or participant to an event. The manager can select and invite participants to the event and the participants and members of the panel management will receive this invitation via email.

Figure 15. The main page and features of an event. The RSVP feature

In addition, the user can define a RSVP (Reservation S'il Vous Plaît) for participants who has been invited to an event.

Under the name and the status of each participant, there is the feature "RSVP" and three colours (Figure 15):

- **Green**: if participant's answer is "yes" (positive).
- **Yellow**: if participant's answer is "Maybe" (participant needs time to decide).
- **Red**: if participants answer is "No" (negative).

By filtering this choice, the user can easily add the availability (positive or negative response to an event) of a participant. For instance, if the user has a phone-communication with a participant who has been invited, and receive participant's negative or positive answer, the user can add the answer to the RSVP as a manager directly. This feature informs about participants answers and availabilities, without the need of participants to log in to the panel management tool and provide their answers. RSVP offers an important feature of the panel management tool in the mitigation of time spending in the process of checking participation availabilities. RSVP also prioritizes the faster and better -almost automated- way to plan and schedule events in the LLs.

3 Technical features of the Panel Management

Panel Management is a Full-Stack Solution that consists of the Back-End, which is responsible for the handling of data, and the Front-End which is a User Interface for the Back-End.

The Back-End:

- Is responsible for any data related action, such as creating, reading, updating and deleting.
- Contains business logic for all transactions, handling as many cases as possible & also preventing errors.
- Uses NestJS. A framework built on top of Node.js, used extensively for scalable, easy to maintain & reliable server-side applications. The whole backend leverages NestJS for all of its functions.
- Is written in Typescript, a strongly typed programming language that makes it easier for teams of people to work on the same code & understand it.
- Makes extensive use of RxJS, a functional reactive programming library meant for writing efficient, asynchronous code. Many API requests make use of RxJs Observables to transform data on a scalable level such as returning lists of users based on a search query, user profile icons etc.
- Makes use of NestJS unit tests together with end-to-end testing (with the help of SuperTest) preventing breaking changes from entering production while ensuring proper behaviour of components. SuperTest is used to test each endpoint separately and check if expected behaviours occur, such as updating a database user with new information. On the other hand, unit tests are more specific by testing individual methods for expected return types and error handling.
- Is directly connected to a MySQL database running InnoDB for storage. Instead of running traditional queries on the database, it uses an ORM tool called TypeORM.
- Uses TypeORM for all database related actions. By using the Data Mapper pattern, Typescript classes can be directly read, stored, updated or deleted from the database as objects, leaving little room for type mismatches or database errors. TypeORM also offers automatically generated migrations, allowing us to trace all database changes to their respective generated migration scripts. Making database changes becomes as easy as changing a property of a typescript class.

The Front-End:

- Is responsible for the presentation of Back-End data to users and for allowing them to manipulate said data.
- Is also responsible for all communications with the Back-End, serving data seamlessly to users.
- Uses Angular. A web application framework built with Typescript. It makes use the Model View Whatever software architectural pattern, allowing tremendous flexibility to use any pattern the developer prefers such as MVC, MVVM etc.

- Also makes use of RxJS for data presentation & scalability. Lists of users, form data, prompts etc all use the Observer pattern and are bound to angular elements which are in turn presented to the user via the User Interface.
- Uses Fuse, a modular template with Angular Material support for most of its UI elements. The look and feel of the web application is governed by Fuse.
- Uses TailwindCSS a CSS framework for maintainable styling and rapid UI development. TailwindCSS allows us to use premade classes in place of custom CSS styling. A multi-line complex CSS style becomes a single word class with the use of TailwindCSS. Responsive Design is also supported, making it easier to quickly style elements for mobile devices and multiple screen sizes.

Makes use Jasmine & Karma for unit tests, preventing breaking changes from entering production.

4 Conclusion

This deliverable was aimed to provide a brief but detailed description of the features, characteristics and abilities of the VITALISE panel management tool.

The panel management tool is developed to facilitate researchers with their research activities in the Living Labs hence, this deliverable has described all its features to clarify the current and the future possibilities and potentialities of the VITALISE panel management tool, not only for research infrastructures, but also in the field of innovative ICT tools.

The VITALISE team aim to keep the panel management tool updated in line with the needs of researchers (that is the main purpose of the feature of feedback), hence we will continue collecting feedback through the process and procedures of the VITALISE project, in order to create an irreplaceable and continuously updated ICT tool.

The basic features as well as the sub-features and characteristics of “contacts”, “projects” and “events” are a strong database in the hands of every researcher. The well-structured and easy menu with the general features (e.g. the lines with which the user magnifies the main screen of the panel) are offering a convenient, but also effective digital experience in anyone’s workplace. As mentioned, our team has further vision regarding a panel management application for iOs and smartphones as one of our next steps. These actions aim to establish the panel management as an innovative ICT tool always in line with the needs of researchers and the demanding research activities of the Living Labs.